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Effects of social media on Basra College Students and their treatment

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to check the level of effects of social media on Basra college students and their treatment and to determine the level of effects of social media according to different variables. The study was designed using a survey form. Participants in the study were 102 students who were randomly chosen from different social and economic areas during the 2019-2020 academic year. As the statistics from social networking sites indicate, young people are among the most Categories are the use of these networks, so they are vulnerable to being affected and affected, cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally. They have before stage Factors related to their ability to handle and keep up with technology and leisure Overwork, in addition to forming many intellectual trends for them.

Keywords: Effects; Social media; Students; Treatment

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Introduction

Project goals

Study was to check the level effects of social media on Basra college students and their treatment.

The most important results

1. University students are among the most important classes on which hopes are for

progress, prosperity, and building the future. Therefore, working on building a balanced personality in university students is a goal that educational institutions seek with all advanced means, through understanding the influences on their condition and building their scientific and cultural system. Include in It has electronic social networks that are now considered one of the most important influences.

2. Detecting the negative effects and positive dimensions of these networks will help educational institutions in reducing negatives and enhancing positives towards the

development of a balanced personality of students Universities.

3. The presence of nursing lessons need more hours than the rest of the lessons through the results of the view of graduates from the College of Nursing Basra.

Introduction

We all recognize this saying but few understand the empowering role social media has played. Through social media, anyone online is empowered by an unrestricted flow of information to add to their knowledge bank. In today's world, it is undeniable that social media plays an important role in impacting our culture, our economy and our overall view of the world. Social media is a new forum that brings people to exchange idea, connect with, relate to, and mobilize for a cause, seek advice, and offer guidance. Social media has removed communication barriers and created decentralized communication channel and open the door for all to have a voice and participate in a democratic fashion including people in repressive countries. This media outlet accommodates a wide variety spontaneous [1]. Adults and children are spending ever-increasing amounts of time 'online'. Across the world, every 60 seconds an estimated 156 million emails are sent, 3.8 million search requests are made on Google and two million minutes of calls are made via Skype, with the average internet user now spending "around 6 hours each day using internet-powered devices and services". 1 Much of this time is also spent on social media. While there is no agreed definition of social media, we have understood it to include "websites and apps that enable users to create and share content or to participate in social networking". 2 We also recognize that the lines have blurred between different types of online media, with some gaming sites, for example, now involving social networking. 3 We are social's Global Digital report estimated that more than 3 billion people globally use social media each month, 4 while in Great Britain the Office for National Statistics

(ONS) reported that 66% of all adults aged 16+, and 96% in the 16-24 age group, had used social networking within the last three months [2]. Social media has exploded as a category of online discourse where people create content, share it, bookmark it and network at a prodigious rate. Because of its ease of use, speed and reach, social media is fast changing the public discourse in society and setting trends and agenda in topics that range from the environment and politics to technology and the entertainment industry (Asur and Huberman, 2010). In the last ten years, the online world has changed dramatically, thanks to the invention of social media, young men and women now exchange ideas, feelings, personal information, pictures and videos at a truly astonishing rate [3]. The growing number of researches on Internet addiction indicates that Internet addiction is a psychosocial disorder and its characteristics are as follows: tolerance, withdrawal symptoms, affective disorders, and problems in social relations. Internet usage creates psychological, social, school and/or work difficulties in a person's life. Internet addiction can make changes in lifestyle and family values [4]. demonstrated that internet addiction is significantly and negatively affect students' academic performance [6]. The Internet era began in the whole world and linking countries together in 1991 and it was the first time that the term web appeared in the world, but now everything in daily life has become communications, education, business and health, as its benefits are numerous, but it is accompanied by Internet issues and problems [5,7].

Methodology

Where the number of samples is 102 and the samples were taken randomly, where the percentage of females was 53 and the proportion of males 49 where the percentage of using the communication for students is 67 of the samples and that the percentage of formation of friends from social networking 48 and when we asked about the impact of social

networking sites on raising the level was 64 and about allocating time far from The use of communication was 51 for the allocation of time sometimes and the opinion of the students was the most that without the use of communication it was sometimes at a rate of 45 and the opinion of the students was when you stopped using and you may find it difficult the opinion of the students was sometimes by 48 and when asked about the cause of social and nervous communication and the aggression was the most beginning result 66 Your academic level is decreased when using social media, sometimes a higher percentage, reaching 46, and on social communication causing health and physical problems. The percentage of 54 is the most, and in addition to you social communication skills means the most often, by 66%, and on the preference of sites, the most constant sites are the most permanent percentage and the percentage 58 The percentage of the goal in using social media was 52%, which means that it is far from education or the social impact effect I am aware of the academic level, the positive impact was 27%, and the negative and positive impact ratio was that of one 39, while the percentage did not affect was 29, where the ratio was acceptable, no effect 3-2 Design of the study: Descriptive, cross sectional study. 3-3 Setting of the study: The study carried out at nursing college / university of Basra-in Al-Basra city from October - 1th-2019 through April 1st-2020. 3-4 Sample of the study: Random sample of 300 students chosen from different schools were collected. 3-5 Instrument of the study Instrument of this study was questionnaire consist. Demographic data: Consist of variables include (Age, Gender, stage). We applied Young's IADQ (1998) to assess symptoms consist of 22 questions scored on a two-point scale [no (0) and yes (1). 1) "Do you use social media?" (2) "Do you think that social media has a role in the development of the individual's personality?" (3) "Does social media influence raise the cultural level?" (4) "Have you been friends with social media?" (5) "Do you devote time to study away from using social media?"

(6) Will life without social media be boring and empty? (7) "When you are on social media, do you find it difficult to stop using it even if you get tired or drowsy?" (8) "Does the use of social media cause you extreme nervousness and aggressive behavior?" (9) "Did you review your educational level while using social media?" (10) Does prolonged social contact cause you physical and health problems? (11) Does your use of social media add your skills and gain a positive impact on the ground? (12) Do you have favorite websites that you visit on social media? (13) How much time do you spend playing electronic games during the day 3-5 Method of data collection the data collected by obtaining formal approval from the Students to answer about the questionnaire through direct interview. Statistical data analysis: The data where analyze by admitted to the Statistical program (SPSS) Program, version 16 for interpretation of result. Through the application of the descriptive data analysis.

Results of the project. Where the number of samples is 102 and the samples were taken randomly, where the percentage of females was 53 and the proportion of males 49 where the percentage of using the communication for students is 67 of the samples and that the percentage of formation of friends from social networking 48 and when we asked about the impact of social networking sites on raising the level was 64 and about allocating time far from The use of communication was 51 for the allocation of time sometimes and the opinion of the students was the most that without the use of communication it was sometimes at a rate of 45 and the opinion of the students was when you stopped using and you may find it difficult the opinion of the students was sometimes by 48 and when asked about the cause of social and nervous communication and the aggression was the most beginning result 66 Your academic level is decreased when using social media, sometimes a higher percentage, reaching 46, and on social communication causing health and physical problems. The percentage of 54 is the most, and in addition to you social

communication skills means the most often, by 66%, and on the preference of sites, the most constant sites are the most permanent percentage and the percentage 58 The percentage of the goal in using social media was 52%, which means that it is far from education or the social impact effect I am aware of the

academic level, the positive impact was 27%, and the negative and positive impact ratio was that of one 39, while the percentage did not affect was 29, where the ratio was acceptable, no effect As in the table number (1) below.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the participants.

Frequency N (%) =	Categories /grouping	Characteristic of participants
49	Male	Gender
53	Female	
79	Single	Age in year
23	Married	
9(3%)	The first is average	Stage of study
25(19%)	The second is average	
29(23%)	The third is average	
39(57%)	The fourth is average	

Discussion of the Results

The Through discussion of the results, it became clear that the samples, which number 102 students, and after sorting the samples students, showed that 66 of the students use chat at an average of six hours a day and 20 use games at an average of six hours, while the rest use the Internet with fewer hours, so the total has become 86 students who are addicted. On the Internet, but for students, which had a total of 100 samples, it turned out that 47 of the students were using games at an average of six hours a day and 38 were using chat at an average of six hours.

VAR00001.

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
1	55	33.3	22.7
2	21	33.3	-11.3-
3	26	33.3	-11.3-
Total	102		

May be	No N (%)	Yes N (%)	Item
			1. Do you use social media?
	13(13%)	33(33%)	
			2. Do you think that social media has a role in the development of the individual's personality?
	23(23%)	46(46%)	
21%)21)			3. Does social media influence raise the cultural level?
	13(13%)	68%(68)	
			4. Have you been friends with social media?
	19%)19)	64(64%)	
			5. Do you devote time to study away from using social media?
	18(18%)	55(55%)	
			6. Will life without social media be boring and empty?
	23(23%)	66(66%)	
			7. When you are on social media, do you find it difficult to stop using it even if you get tired or drowsy?
	19(19%)	67(67%)	
			8. Does the use of social media cause you extreme nervousness and aggressive behavior?
	33%)33)	47%(47)	
			9. Did you review your educational level while using social media?
	36%)36)	44(44%)	
			10. Did you review your educational level while using social media?
	27%)27)	58%(58)	
			11. Does your use of social media add your skills and gain a positive impact on the ground?
	29%)29)	46%(46)	
			12. Do you have favorite websites that you visit on social media?
	29(29%)	53(53%)	
			13. How much time do you spend playing electronic games?
14(%14)	15(14%)	73(72%)	
309	297	720*	Total
	-21.40%	-54.80%	

* p≤0.005

Test Statistics.	
	VAR00001
Chi-Square	23.120 ^a
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000
cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 33.3.	

Conclusion

The person should set strict and strict rules to reduce the amount of time spent on communication sites, It is useful to set time intervals in which the person is absent from all media and communication, creating periods of "fasting" They must find what they occupy themselves and their lives, and this is a very important element in the treatment, One should give priority to real life as a commitment to friends with wonderful relationships, and it will not happen without spending time with them. The place of work is not like the beach, and the sleep time is not like the time of sport and recovery. Remove people who do not care about your page. Be sure this is a great opportunity to learn about other useful sites, there are open learning sites. You must exercise until you get rid of using the equipment.

1. The person should set strict and strict rules to reduce the amount of time spent on communication sites,
2. It is useful to set time intervals in which the person is absent from all media and communication, creating periods of "fasting"
3. They must find what they occupy themselves and their lives, and this is a very important element in the treatment.
4. You should give priority to real life as a commitment to friends with wonderful relationships, and it will not happen without spending time with them. The place of work is not like the beach, and the sleep time is not like the time of sport and recovery.

5. Remove people who do not care about your page.

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